

**TURBINE NOZZLE GUIDE VANE ENDWALL AEROTHERMAL PERFORMANCE WITH
PULSATILE FLOW INDUCED BY HYDROGEN COMBUSTION**

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ABSTRACT

Due to its superior thermodynamic properties and zero-carbon emission characteristics, hydrogen combustion in gas turbines is being actively promoted as a promising strategy for achieving worldwide decarbonization goals. However, significantly intensified flow pulsations represent a major obstacle. To clarify the impacts of flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion on the turbine endwall aerothermal performance, the URANS numerical predictions and FFT spectral analysis were performed in this paper, based on measured flow pulsation data from realistic hydrogen combustion tests. This study systematically investigated the impacts of pulsation frequencies ($f = 1000$ Hz, 3000 Hz, and 5000 Hz) and pulsation amplitudes ($K = 5\%$ and 10%) on the endwall secondary flow fields and film cooling performance at design conditions. Key findings revealed that flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion are detrimental to the endwall film cooling performance and potentially contribute to a non-monotonic decrease in film cooling effectiveness of 3.8% - 10.1% as pulsation frequencies increase. At low pulsation amplitude conditions ($K = 5\%$), the maximum and minimum reductions in endwall film cooling effectiveness are observed at $f = 3000$ Hz and 5000 Hz, respectively. Increased pulsation amplitudes ($K = 10\%$) will introduce additional degradation in endwall film cooling performance, and the reduction magnitudes present distinct frequency sensitivity, with responses ranging from 14.2% to 0.2% . Fluctuation peaks in film cooling effectiveness are found in regions downstream of film holes, near the vane pressure side and vane passage throat, and pitch-averaged fluctuation magnitudes are less than 10% within the vane passage. Notably, flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion propagate through turbine cascades without frequency attenuation, as revealed by spectral analysis.

Keywords: Hydrogen-combusted turbine, Turbine endwall, Unsteady aerothermal performance, Flow pulsation

NOMENCLATURE

C	chord (m)
CV	cavity vortex
C_x	axial chord (m)
$CRVP$	counter-rotating vortex pair
D	diameter (m)
DR	density ratio
f	frequency (Hz)
HV	horse-shoe vortex
K	inlet pulsation amplitude
LE	leading edge
MFR	mass flow ratio
NGV	nozzle guide vane
P	pitch (m)
Pr	relative pressure (%)
S	span (m)
SV	secondary vortex
T	temperature (K)
T_p	time periodic
Tu	turbulence intensity (%)

Greek

η	film cooling effectiveness
η_r	relative film cooling effectiveness (%)
$\bar{\eta}$	pitch-averaged film cooling effectiveness
$\bar{\bar{\eta}}$	area-averaged film cooling effectiveness

Subscripts

aw	adiabatic wall
avg	time averaged
r	relative
c	coolant jets
f	film cooled

1. INTRODUCTION

International climate goals and increasingly stringent regulations on greenhouse gas emissions necessitate practical approaches in the gas turbine industry to minimize greenhouse gas emissions, especially of CO₂ [1]. To achieve worldwide decarbonization objectives, two main pathways are being pursued: combustion of low-carbon or even zero-carbon fuels and carbon capture and sequestration. Due to its superior thermodynamic properties and zero-carbon emission characteristics, hydrogen combustion in gas turbines is being actively explored as a promising strategy to mitigate CO₂ emissions from power generation. Nevertheless, compared to conventional fossil fuels, the phenomenon of flow pulsations is significantly intensified at the combustor exit when hydrogen is added, due to variations in the combustion behavior [2-3]. This results in substantial changes in the flow patterns and aerothermal performance of the downstream turbine nozzle guide vane (NGV) cascades.

High-efficiency film cooling layouts, as a key thermal protection technology, can realize controllable thermal loads on turbine cascades and ensure adequate component life in extreme operating conditions. Variations in the vane thermal load distributions induced by hydrogen combustion necessitate novel and higher-efficiency film cooling schemes, particularly for endwall regions with high inflow sensitivity. The presence of strong, unsteady, and three-dimensional secondary flows near the endwall poses additional challenges in achieving effective film cooling and makes endwall thermal management a major research interest. Based on comprehensive review of previous literature [4-5] and thorough understanding of the complicated endwall flow fields, researchers attempted to control local flow patterns and thermal load distributions by refining endwall profiles. A detailed comparison of endwall aerothermal performance with different endwall profiles has been investigated by Thrift et al. [6], Hussain et al. [7], Chen et al. [8], and Bai et al. [9]. These investigations demonstrated that the converging profiles contribute to reducing the intensity of the passage vortex and endwall crossflow by thinning the inflow boundary layer. Compared to simplified flat endwall, the significant enlargement of coolant jet coverage and enhancement of film cooling effectiveness are observed on the contoured endwall, especially in regions around the vane leading edge (LE) and downstream of the vane passage throat.

Aiming to improve endwall film cooling performance and prolong turbine component life, numerous film cooling layouts have been innovated, and systematic studies of their film cooling characteristics were conducted at conventional fossil fuel combustion conditions. Han et al. [10] and Plczak et al. [11] reviewed advanced film cooling techniques within gas turbine cascades and highlighted key future directions and challenges in turbine cascade cooling designs. Endwall film cooling performance with various hole arrangements has been compared and analyzed by Chowdhury et al. [12], Knost et al. [13], Shiau et al. [14], and Hu and An [15]. These studies investigated endwall film cooling patterns using experimental and numerical methods, and found that an appropriate film hole design can

markedly enhance endwall film cooling performance. Through comparative analysis, the axial film hole layout promotes better migration of coolant jets and provides superior endwall film coverage. Liu et al. [16] and Yang et al. [17] incorporated both endwall pressure and velocity distributions into film hole layout optimization. Endwall film cooling performance was analyzed with reference design, pressure coefficient-based layout, and iso-Mach number-based layout. These studies revealed that film holes aligned with pressure coefficient lines and iso-Mach number lines can provide improved uniformity in film coverage and enhance film cooling performance, compared to conventional axial arrangement.

Two primary variations are noticed with hydrogen combustion: gas composition (higher proportion of water vapor in combustion products) and intensified flow pulsations, which undoubtedly alter the aerothermal performance of downstream turbine vane cascade. Chiesa et al. [3] and Gazzani et al. [18] theoretically investigated the impacts of hydrogen-enriched fossil fuels on turbine cascade aerothermal performance, and found that increased moisture levels in combustion gas result in a lower turbine inflow rate. This may compromise compressor and turbine matching characteristics, leading to component misalignment and increased cascade thermal loads. Focusing on the higher water vapor content in hydrogen combustion products, Wang et al. [19], Han et al. [20], and Du et al. [21] evaluated turbine cascade film cooling performance at different water vapor concentration conditions. These studies highlighted that the decrease in cascade film cooling effectiveness associated with increased water vapor concentration is attributed to changes in the constant-pressure specific heat of the mainstream. Comparative analyses of multi-stage turbine cascade aerothermal performance between conventional fossil fuels and hydrogen combustion were conducted by Kim et al. [22] and Bandini et al. [23]. These studies indicated that the averaged heat flux and heat transfer coefficient are significantly enhanced (by approximately 10%) in the first-stage turbines, whereas they rapidly decrease in the second-stage turbines compared to conventional fossil fuels.

Gas thermoacoustic oscillations triggered by coupled heat release and acoustic vibrations in combustors are typical in realistic gas turbine operations and propagate through downstream turbine cascades as quasi-sinusoidal wave patterns with frequencies of 8 - 1200 Hz [24]. To estimate film cooling performance at pulsatile inflow conditions, two approaches have been widely adopted: unsteady simulations and low-frequency oscillatory equipment ($f = 0-35$ Hz) in test facilities. Ligrani et al. [25-26] were early interested in the flow pulsation phenomenon and conducted film cooling effectiveness measurements on simplified flat plates at low-frequency pulsation conditions (0.2-8 Hz), and revealed that pressure fluctuations induced by the mainstream will bring unsteady behavior in coolant jet trajectories and momentum. Numerical and experimental studies at higher pulsation frequencies (16-2144 Hz) were subsequently performed by Borup et al. [27], Ma et al. [28], and Baek and Yavuzkurt [29]. These studies showed that mainstream oscillations will promote coolant jet separation

and reattachment, significantly alter downstream counter-rotating vortex pair (CRVP) patterns and increase unsteadiness in film cooling. In addition, film cooling performance presents strong sensitivity to pulsation frequencies, and trends in film cooling effectiveness can be classified into four regimes characterized by decreasing and increasing interactions. Intensified pressure and temperature pulsation phenomenon was observed at the combustor exit when hydrogen was added, and the peak points increased by approximately 50% with increasing hydrogen content [30]. Furthermore, higher pulsation frequencies (approximately 40% higher than those of conventional fossil fuels) were also detected in hydrogen-enriched combustors [31]. While the introduction of hydrogen as a substitute for conventional fossil fuels can minimize CO₂ emissions from gas turbines, the more intensive pulsation effects associated with altered combustion behavior should not be neglected. Accomplishing uniform and effective film cooling on endwall remains challenging, and pulsatile inflow brings additional challenges in organizing coolant jet coverage. Therefore, it is essential to conduct further extensive and in-depth research on turbine endwall aerothermal performance with pulsatile flow induced by hydrogen combustion.

In general, most previous studies concerned the aerothermal performance of simplified flat plates at low-frequency pulsation conditions, and extremely few investigations were performed in realistic turbine cascades. Furthermore, current research on endwall aerothermal performance of hydrogen-combustion turbines remains highly limited, and coolant jet flow behavior at pulsatile conditions is not yet well understood. In this paper, based on measured flow pulsation data induced by hydrogen combustion, the endwall aerothermal performance of the NGV modeled by an industrial turbine cascade was studied at three typical pulsation frequencies ($f = 1000$ Hz, 3000 Hz, and 5000 Hz) and two pulsation amplitudes (5% and 10% of inlet total temperature and total pressure). This study reveals near-endwall flow behavior at pulsatile flow conditions and endwall film cooling effectiveness distributions in hydrogen-combustion turbines. Furthermore, this work also contributes to clarifying endwall aerothermal performance discrepancy between no-pulsation and inflow pulsation conditions, aiming to provide insightful references for industrial designers developing film cooling layouts for hydrogen-combustion turbine cascades.

2. EXPERIMENT AND COMPUTATION SETUP

2.1 Experimental Facility

Endwall film cooling performance at no-pulsation condition was measured in the transonic wind tunnel at Virginia Tech University, and the test section contained six equally spaced vanes with a span of 152.4 mm, forming five complete cascade passages. The NGV test cascade with converging endwall profiles and a double-row discrete film hole layout was drawn from a realistic industry gas turbine, as shown in Fig.1. The test cascade was scaled up by a factor of 1.5 from the actual vane cascade to match the similar flow conditions (exit Reynolds number Re_{ex} and exit Mach number Ma_{ex}). A gap located $0.88 Cx$ upstream of the vane leading edge (LE), which represents the

combustor-NGV interface, was included in the test cascade. The staggered cylindrical film holes with a diameter of 2.4 mm and an injection angle $\alpha = 50$ deg were adopted. The upstream film holes (row 1) and downstream film holes (row 2) were positioned at $0.46 Cx$ and $0.3 Cx$ upstream of the vane LE, respectively, as marked in Fig.2. Detailed geometric parameters of this test cascade are listed in Table 1.

To accurately capture endwall aerothermal performance at high Ma_{ex} conditions, two independent experimental measurements were conducted in this transonic wind tunnel, under identical mainstream conditions and coolant supply pressure, with different coolant temperatures applied. During each test, the transient infrared (IR) thermography technique was adopted, and time-varying temperature data were recorded through an optical window. The heat flux (q) at each pixel was then reconstructed from IR temperature traces using a one-dimensional semi-infinite conduction model. Subsequently, the dual-linear regression technique (DLRT) proposed by Xue et al. [33] was adopted to acquire the target parameters of endwall heat transfer coefficient (h) and film cooling effectiveness (η). Detailed descriptions of the wind tunnel design, operating conditions, measurement procedures, and data reduction techniques can be referred to Refs. [32-33].

Fig.1 Experimental test section and film hole arrangement

Fig.2 Geometry of turbine NGV cascade

Table 1 Geometrical parameters of NGV cascade

Parameters	Value
Vane chord (C)/mm	91.2
Axial chord (Cx)/mm	50
Vane pitch (P)/mm	83.14
Vane span (S)/mm	152.4
Injection angle (α)/(deg)	50
Film hole diameter (D)/mm	2.4
Film hole P/D	3.5
Exit Mach number (Ma)	0.85

2.2 Computation Model and Mesh

Based on the geometric model of the test cascade, a single-passage computational model was established, comprising the vane profile, endwall profile, 20 double-row staggered cylindrical film holes, and a coolant supply cavity. To enhance numerical stability and prevent undesired backflow, an extension of $0.6 Cx$ was applied to both the computational domain inlet and outlet, as indicated in Fig.3. The multi-block structured meshes were generated using ICEM CFD, and the translational periodic conditions were imposed in the pitch-wise direction. The regions around the film holes and vane were filled with O-type grids to ensure superior grid quality and wall coverage. To capture flow behavior near the endwall and flow field pulsation characteristics, localized grid refinement was strategically applied to the endwall and vane surfaces, as illustrated in Fig.3. Additionally, the first endwall cell height (approximately 1.5×10^{-6} m) and a small expansion factor (about 1.12) was adopted in computational meshes to satisfy the requirement of wall maximum y^+ .

Fig.3 Computational model and mesh of vane cascade

To obtain mesh-independent prediction results, the pitch-averaged film cooling effectiveness ($\bar{\eta}$) was extracted, and the relationship between mesh node number and $\bar{\eta}$ at no-pulsation conditions is illustrated in Fig.4. Based on grid-independent analysis, the statistical size of 12×10^6 nodes, including about 8.8×10^6 nodes for the vane passage and 3.2×10^6 nodes for the coolant supply cavity, can provide an optimal balance between prediction accuracy and computational cost, and is fine enough to obtain endwall aerothermal performance in this study.

Fig.4 Pitch-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness with different mesh node number

2.3 Numerical Method

The endwall secondary flow fields and film cooling effectiveness were obtained via solving unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equations using ANSYS

Fluent. The turbulence model of realizable $k-\epsilon$, accounting for compressibility effects, curvature correction, viscous heating effects, and production limiter, was activated to de-close the equation systems. The ideal gas modeled by air was employed as the working fluid in the computational domain, and the viscosity, thermal conductivity, and specific heat were determined by kinetic theory. The transient pressure-velocity coupling method with an overall accuracy of second-order upwind was adopted in this paper. The transient time step size was dynamically adjusted from 1×10^{-6} s to 5×10^{-6} s according to the inflow pulsation frequencies. Several preliminary computations were conducted, and eventually each pulsation period was discretized into 200-time steps with 10 internal iterations. Multiple pressure and temperature monitors were positioned within the vane passage to assess convergence, and the convergent values of normalized residuals were set to 10^{-6} . Additionally, the convergence criterion also required that the difference in time-averaged values between consecutive periods was less than 0.1%.

The computational boundary conditions were derived from experimental measurements conducted in the transonic wind tunnel at Virginia Tech University. The total temperature and total pressure profiles were measured and applied to the computational inlet, as shown in Fig.5. The turbulence intensity (16%) and integral length scale (3 mm) were kept constant across the vane spanwise direction and equal to the measured values via a hot-wire probe. The averaged total pressure was applied to the coolant supply cavity inlet, and an averaged constant pressure condition was set at the vane passage outlet. In the numerical predictions, all computational domain walls were defined as adiabatic and no-slip boundaries. Additional computational boundary conditions are provided in Table 2.

Fig.5 Inlet total temperature and total pressure profiles

Table 2 Computational boundary conditions

Parameters	Value/Description
Working fluid	Ideal gas
Mainstream inlet	Measured total temperature and total pressure
Turbulent intensity (Tu)/%	16
Turbulence scale/mm	3
Mainstream outlet	Averaged pressure
Coolant inlet	Measured total pressure
Coolant inlet temperature/K	298
Domain wall	Adiabatic
Design mass flow ratio (MFR)	1.9%
Density ratio (DR)	1.2

Based on measured flow pulsation data from realistic hydrogen combustion tests, three typical pulsation frequencies ($f = 1000$ Hz, 3000 Hz, and 5000 Hz) and two pulsation amplitudes

($K = 5\%$ and 10%) were observed and extracted. The quasi-sinusoidal pulsations associated with hydrogen combustion were simplified and implemented by the temporally resolved sinusoidal modulation. The pulsation amplitudes were considered in spatially resolved distributions, and the profiles along the spanwise direction at the computational model inlet are illustrated in Fig.6.

The governing equations for flow pulsation conditions at the mainstream inlet are defined as:

$$T_{t,in} = (1 + K(2\pi \times f \times t)) \times T_{t,in} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{t,in} = (1 + K(2\pi \times f \times t)) \times P_{t,in} \quad (2)$$

where $T_{t,in}$ and $P_{t,in}$ are the measured total temperature and total pressure during typical test duration, respectively.

Fig.6 Pulsatile flow conditions at the turbine inlet

The film cooling effectiveness (η), as a key parameter for quantifying coolant jets spread and evaluating film cooling performance, is determined by local recovery temperature (T_r), near-endwall film temperature (T_f), and coolant jets temperature (T_c). Due to the inability to directly obtain local T_r , an approximation method was proposed by Li et al. [34] by adding the no coolant flow condition. The T_r was believed to be approximately equal to the adiabatic wall temperature ($T_{aw,0}$) at no coolant condition. Similarly, the T_f was determined by the adiabatic wall temperature ($T_{aw,c}$) with coolant jets.

For each numerical case, two independent CFD simulations were performed with the same mainstream and surface thermal boundary conditions (adiabatic no-slip wall). The adiabatic wall temperatures ($T_{aw,0}$ and $T_{aw,c}$) were drawn at different coolant supply conditions, specifically, no coolant flow and design pressure flow conditions. Subsequently, the film cooling effectiveness can be calculated by the following Eq. (3).

$$\eta = \frac{T_r - T_f}{T_r - T_c} = \frac{T_{aw,0} - T_{aw,c}}{T_{aw,0} - T_c} \quad (3)$$

where T_c is the coolant temperature.

To more comprehensively evaluate endwall film cooling performance in pulsatile flow fields, the time-averaged film cooling effectiveness (η_{avg}) and instantaneous film cooling effectiveness (η) are defined by Eqs. (4) and (5), respectively.

$$\eta_{ave} = \frac{\frac{1}{Tp} \int_t^{t+Tp} T_{aw,0} - \frac{1}{Tp} \int_t^{t+Tp} T_{aw,c}}{\frac{1}{Tp} \int_t^{t+Tp} T_{aw,0} - \frac{1}{Tp} \int_t^{t+Tp} T_c} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_t = \frac{(T_{aw,0})_t - (T_{aw,c})_t}{(T_{aw,0})_t - T_c} \quad (5)$$

where Tp is the pulsation period.

2.4 Numerical Method Validation

Detailed and comprehensive validation of the turbulence model for steady simulation has been conducted by Li et al. [34]. The realizable $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model demonstrates superior performance in predicting coolant jet lift-off, reattachment, and interactions between mainstream and coolant jets, and can provide the most reasonable prediction of endwall film cooling effectiveness distributions. Therefore, the credibility of the unsteady prediction method is evaluated, and discrepancies between experimental data and numerical predictions are highlighted in this section.

Figure 7 shows film cooling effectiveness distributions at no-pulsation and design coolant delivery conditions ($MFR = 1.9\%$ and $DR = 1.2$). Through qualitative comparison of experimental data and numerical predictions, both the distributions and magnitudes of film cooling effectiveness present a high degree of similarity. Since the endwall region near the vane suction side was partially obstructed in the experiment, film cooling effectiveness along the middle-pitch streamline ($0.5P$) was extracted for quantitative analysis to determine the numerical prediction error. A quantitative comparison of endwall film cooling effectiveness is illustrated in Fig.8. At the vane passage ($0 < x < 0.65Cx$), which is of interest in this paper, endwall film cooling effectiveness remains within the experimental uncertainty ($\Delta\eta = \pm 0.1$) and maximum error is limited to 15%.

The rough surface will decrease film cooling effectiveness in regions downstream of the vane passage ($x > 0.65Cx$), due to combined effects of thicker boundary layer and faster dissipation of coolant jets. Inadequate consideration of the interactions between coolant jets and the mainstream in the turbulence model also contributes to the numerical prediction errors, especially in regions downstream of film holes ($x < 0.2Cx$). Therefore, the deviations between experimental measurements and predicted magnitudes is suggested to be caused by smooth wall treatment in numerical simulations and accuracy limitations of the turbulence model.

Fig.7 Time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness distributions

Fig.8 Time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness along middle pitch streamline

Figure 9 shows experimental measurement and numerical prediction results of endwall flow physics, and a detailed comparative analysis is provided in this section. During the test duration, an oil paint visualization technique was employed to capture near-endwall vortex systems, coolant jet separation, and migration behavior. Prior to each blowdown test, oil paints of different colors were applied at several positions on the endwall, including regions downstream of film holes, the vane pressure side, and suction side. The flow behavior near the endwall can be depicted by the oil paints after testing, as shown in Fig.9. The stagnation position, horse-shoe vortex (HV) system, and coolant jet coverage are clearly demonstrated by the ring-shaped regions around the vane LE and the striped patterns on the endwall. Qualitative comparison shows that the numerical predictions have similar flow field structures near the endwall to experimental observations. In general, the present numerical method can reliably capture both near-endwall flow behavior and film cooling effectiveness distributions.

Fig.9 Near-endwall flow fields between EXP and CFD.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phenomenon of flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion significantly affects endwall aerothermal performance of downstream turbine vane cascades. Detailed discussion of near-endwall flow behavior and endwall film cooling effectiveness at three typical pulsation frequencies ($f = 1000$ Hz, 3000 Hz, and 5000 Hz) and two pulsation amplitudes ($K = 5\%$ and 10%) is presented in this section. In addition, the fast Fourier transform (FFT) method is also adopted to capture and extract spectral features from fluctuation signals at multiple near-endwall monitoring locations within the vane passage.

3.1 Effects of Inflow Pulsation Frequency

The initial efforts are made to clarify the impacts of inflow pulsation frequency triggered by hydrogen combustion, focusing on low pulsation amplitude conditions ($K = 5\%$). Figure 10 presents time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness

distributions at three typical pulsation frequencies, and the endwall film cooling performance at the reference no-pulsation conditions is also provided for comparative analysis. Variations in film cooling performance are emphasized in three key regions: region A within the vane passage ($0 < x < 0.65Cx$), which is of interest in this paper, region B around the vane LE, and region C downstream of the vane passage throat ($x > 0.65 Cx$).

Fig.10 Time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness distributions at various pulsation frequency conditions

Region A: Inflow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion significantly diminish endwall film cooling performance, leading to dramatic expansion of the wedge-shaped poor-coverage region size in the middle of the vane passage and contraction of high-effectiveness region size around the vane pressure side. As pulsation frequencies increase, a non-monotonic response in both film coverage size and film cooling effectiveness is observed. The minimum film cooling performance degradation is obtained at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions, which maintains a comparable magnitude of film cooling effectiveness to no-pulsation conditions. At lower ($f = 1000$ Hz) or higher ($f = 5000$ Hz) pulsation frequencies, endwall film cooling effectiveness further decreases, and the magnitudes of film cooling effectiveness drop to 0.4 in most endwall regions at $f = 5000$ Hz conditions. This indicates that inflow pulsations will weaken the thermal protection capabilities of original film cooling layouts, and novel and pulsation-resistant film cooling schemes should be redesigned for hydrogen-combustion turbine cascades.

Region B: Inflow pulsations have a minimal impact on endwall film cooling performance around the vane LE, and the magnitudes remain relatively stable at $f = 1000$ Hz and 3000 Hz conditions. Compared to the no-pulsation conditions, a relatively obvious decrease in film cooling effectiveness levels is found at

$f = 5000$ Hz conditions, especially in regions near the vane suction side.

Region C: At no-pulsation conditions, the endwall downstream of the vane passage is well covered by coolant jets and indicates good film cooling effectiveness with a magnitude of 0.4–0.5. When flow pulsations are introduced, endwall film cooling performance deteriorates at a visible rate, accompanied by a significant decrease in film cooling effectiveness. The decay amplitudes present comparable behavior to those in Region B, demonstrating non-monotonic response to increasing pulsation frequencies. The worst coolant jet coverage is noticed at $f = 5000$ Hz conditions, and this region is dominated by stripes with low film cooling effectiveness (less than 0.3).

Figures 11-13 present the variations in endwall film cooling effectiveness throughout one pulsation period at three typical pulsation frequencies ($f = 1000$ Hz, 3000 Hz, and 5000 Hz) and low pulsation amplitude conditions ($K = 5\%$). The parameter, relative film cooling effectiveness (η_r), is used to evaluate the fluctuation magnitudes in pulsatile flow fields and is defined as follows:

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta_t - \eta_{ave}}{\eta_{ave}} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

where η_t is the instantaneous endwall film cooling effectiveness, and η_{ave} represents the time-averaged endwall film cooling.

As illustrated in Figs.11-13, lower endwall relative film cooling effectiveness, representing relatively weak fluctuations, is observed in most regions of the vane passage ($0 < x < 0.65Cx$) and downstream of the vane passage throat ($x > 0.65Cx$), and the amplitudes are limited to approximately 5% at 0 and $0.5Tp$ for all pulsation frequencies. Due to variations in coolant jet flow behavior, the regions downstream of the film holes ($-0.2Cx < x < 0$) present higher endwall relative film cooling effectiveness with magnitudes of 10%. At strong pulsation phases of $0.25Tp$ and $0.75Tp$, the fluctuations in film cooling performance are significantly enhanced, where endwall relative film cooling effectiveness exceeds 10% in the vane passage and even surpasses 15% in regions downstream of film holes. It is worth noting that several regions with fluctuation peaks can be identified, particularly in regions downstream of film holes, near the vane pressure side, and around the vane passage throat.

As inflow pulsation frequencies increase, there is a similar non-monotonic trend in endwall relative film cooling effectiveness, which first decreases then increases. Within the vane passage, which is of interest in this paper, the most negligible fluctuation in endwall film cooling performance is obtained at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions. At higher inflow pulsation frequency conditions ($f = 5000$ Hz), the alternating in-phase and anti-phase fluctuation patterns are observed within vane passage. Additionally, pulsations gradually accumulate toward the vane pressure or suction side, resulting in lateral alternating behavior in endwall relative film cooling effectiveness.

Variations in endwall film cooling performance can be explained by the pulsatile characteristics of secondary flow fields near the endwall and coolant jet behavior. Figure 14 shows the spanwise temperature fields, pressure fields, and near-

endwall streamline distributions along Plane 1 (position illustrated in Fig.10) at strong pulsation phases of $0.25Tp$ and $0.75Tp$.

Fig.11 Endwall relative film cooling effectiveness distributions at $f = 1000$ Hz conditions

Fig.12 Endwall relative film cooling effectiveness distributions at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions

Fig.13 Endwall relative film cooling effectiveness distributions at $f = 5000$ Hz conditions

The relative pressure (Pr) is employed to quantify the pressure fluctuation amplitude and is calculated by Eq. (7).

$$Pr = \frac{P_t - P_{ave}}{P_{ave}} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

where P is the instantaneous static pressure, and P_{ave} denotes the time-averaged static pressure over the pulsation period.

When mainstream passes through the upstream step, low-energy fluid in the boundary layer enters the gap cavity and induces formation of an intense recirculation region and vortex system, known as the cavity vortex (CV). Small-scale CV remains confined within the gap cavity downstream of step geometry and will hardly impact the downstream coolant jet behavior. As marked in Figs.14(a) and 14(b), the CV is not significantly enhanced by flow pulsations and does not extend to the film hole region at $f = 1000$ Hz and $f = 3000$ Hz conditions. Furthermore, constant negative relative pressure (Pr) is observed at $0.25 T_p$, suggesting increased coolant jet delivery and intensified interactions between coolant jets and mainstream. High-momentum coolant jets can suppress the horse-shoe vortex (HV) system generated by stagnation effects at the vane LE and enhance coolant jet coverage capability, resulting in positive endwall relative film cooling effectiveness, as shown in Fig.11. Similarly, constant positive relative pressure increases the challenge of supplying coolant jets and drives them closer to the endwall at $0.75 T_p$, as shown in Figs.14(a) and 14(b). In the region between film holes and the vane LE, the later migration of HV system creates a small recirculation region, forming secondary vortex system (SV). This will promote coolant jet lift-off and increase dissipation of coolant jet momentum. Therefore,

endwall film cooling performance fluctuations within the vane passage result from combined impacts of coolant jet flow rate, HV system, SV system, and interactions between coolant jets and mainstream. Comparing Figs.14 (a) and (b), relative pressure levels show a significant reduction at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions. This suggests that pulsation behavior of coolant jets is severely weakened, leading to minimal degradation in endwall film cooling performance (as illustrated in Fig.10).

At higher inflow pulsation frequency conditions ($f = 5000$ Hz), opposite pressure fluctuations are presented in regions upstream and downstream of the film holes, as shown in Fig.14 (c). The negative relative pressure around the gap cavity provides an opportunity for the CV development at $0.25 T_p$, and large-scale CV reaches the film hole region and obstructs the migration of coolant jets. Additionally, due to significantly higher positive relative pressure around the film holes, fewer coolant jets can be delivered, resulting in markedly negative relative film cooling effectiveness downstream of the film holes ($-0.2 Cx < x < 0$, as shown in Fig.13). At $0.75 T_p$, the reverse fluctuation patterns reduce adverse effects of the CV and provide a more abundant supply of coolant jets. Nevertheless, significantly intensified SV system contributes to rapid dissipation of the coolant jet momentum, leading to significant degradation of film cooling performance in the vane passage and downstream of the vane passage throat at $f = 5000$ Hz conditions (as shown in Fig.10).

Fig.14 Relative pressure, temperature and spanwise streamline distributions along Plane 1 at various pulsation frequencies

To further quantify fluctuation behavior in endwall film cooling performance, pitch-averaged endwall relative film cooling effectiveness over the pulsation period at various pulsation frequencies is presented in Fig.15. Within the vane passage of interest in this paper, fluctuation peaks are acquired at $0.25 T_p$ and $0.75 T_p$, and the values are limited to below 10%. The pulsation frequencies have minimal impacts on fluctuation amplitudes, but significantly alters fluctuation peak positions. At $f = 1000$ Hz conditions, uniform relative film cooling effectiveness is observed from the vane LE to the vane passage throat, while the fluctuation magnitudes gradually increase at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions, and the peak is attained around the vane passage throat. Relative cooling effectiveness displays alternating fluctuation patterns at $f = 5000$ Hz conditions, with magnitudes of 7% around the vane LE.

Fig.15 Pitch-averaged endwall relative film cooling distributions

Figure 16 illustrates the area-averaged distributions of time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness at no-pulsation and pulsatile inflow conditions. Area-averaged film cooling effectiveness is obviously decreased when flow pulsations are triggered, and exhibits non-monotonic response with increasing pulsation frequencies. Due to dramatically weakened pulsation behavior, minimal degradation in endwall film cooling performance is obtained at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions, and the

magnitudes decrease by approximately 3.8%. As inflow pulsation frequencies increase ($f = 5000$ Hz), endwall film cooling effectiveness decreases rapidly by more than 10%.

Fig.16 Area-averaged distributions of time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness

In summary, inflow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion have significantly negative effects on endwall film cooling performance, with decay exhibiting strong frequency-dependent behavior. With increasing pulsation frequencies, reduction in endwall film cooling effectiveness first diminishes then increases, and a minimum drop of approximately 3.8% is obtained at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions. At higher pulsation frequency ($f = 5000$ Hz), the capability of coolant jet coverage deteriorates severely with film cooling effectiveness decreasing by more than 10%. Despite minimal effects of pulsation frequencies on fluctuation amplitudes in endwall film cooling performance, pulsation frequencies significantly alter fluctuation patterns and promote alternating fluctuation development. Furthermore, fluctuation peaks consistently occur in regions downstream of film holes, near the vane pressure side, and around the vane passage throat. This suggests that film cooling benefits of original layouts will be significantly diminished at pulsatile conditions, thereby increasing thermal failure risks in turbine components. Therefore, novel and pulsation-resistant film cooling schemes should be redesigned for hydrogen-combustion turbine cascades.

3.2 Effect of Inflow Pulsation Amplitude

To comprehensively understand the effects of flow pulsations, endwall film cooling performance is comparatively analyzed between low pulsation amplitude ($K = 5\%$) and high pulsation amplitude ($K = 10\%$) conditions, and the time-averaged film cooling effectiveness is illustrated in Fig.17. Similarly, variations in film cooling effectiveness are discussed in detail for the three key regions.

Region A: Increased pulsation amplitudes further weaken the thermal protection capability of coolant jets, specifically the further shrinkage of well-covered region size and rapid enlargement of poorly-covered region size. At $f = 1000$ Hz conditions, regions near the vane pressure side and suction side that provide high film cooling effectiveness almost totally

disappear, and overall film cooling effectiveness levels drop to 0.2-0.3. As shown in Fig.17 (b), although the film cooling effectiveness further decreases, typical bands with high film cooling effectiveness are retained within the vane passage at $f=3000$ Hz conditions. At higher pulsation frequency ($f=5000$ Hz) conditions, endwall film cooling patterns are modified at high pulsation amplitude, yielding two wedge-shaped poor-coverage regions and extending toward the vane passage throat.

Region B: At $f=1000$ Hz and $f=3000$ Hz conditions, endwall film cooling performance around the vane LE will be reduced by increased pulsation amplitudes, yet the magnitudes of reduction in film cooling effectiveness gradually decrease as pulsation frequencies increase. A significant enhancement in film cooling effectiveness is observed under $f=5000$ Hz conditions, and the magnitudes are even superior to 0.6 at some critical positions.

Fig.17 Time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness distributions at two pulsation amplitudes

Region C: When high pulsation amplitudes are induced, the migration capability of coolant jets is severely weakened, leading to significantly reduced film cooling effectiveness in regions downstream of the vane passage throat. The most terrible coolant jet coverage is acquired at $f=1000$ Hz conditions, and low film cooling effectiveness (0.2-0.3) pervades the entire region. A relatively modest degradation in film cooling performance is noticed at $f=5000$ Hz conditions, demonstrating size shrinkage in the striped regions with high film cooling effectiveness.

Figure 18 presents the area-averaged distributions of time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness at low and high pulsation amplitude conditions. Endwall film cooling performance will further deteriorate as pulsation amplitudes increase, and the magnitudes in reduction present distinct frequency sensitivity. With increasing pulsation frequency from $f=1000$ Hz to $f=5000$ Hz, discrepancies in film cooling effectiveness decrease rapidly from 14.2% to 0.2%. This indicates that additional degradation introduced by high pulsation amplitudes is significantly mitigated at higher pulsation frequency conditions. Furthermore, compared to low pulsation amplitude conditions, the trend in endwall film cooling performance presents distinct behavior. This study represents an initial effort to elucidate the effects of flow pulsations triggered by hydrogen combustion by decoupling pulsation frequencies and pulsation amplitudes. The detailed flow fields near the endwall, secondary flow patterns, coolant jet behavior, and mixing characteristics will be provided in the future studies.

Fig.18 Discrepancies in area-averaged distributions of time-averaged endwall film cooling effectiveness

3.3 Spectral Analysis of Inflow Pulsations

Transient response characteristics of coolant jet flow rate and endwall film cooling performance are discussed by employing FFT analysis. Multiple monitors are placed on the endwall within the computational domain to capture spectral features. Figures 19 (a) and 19 (b) present fluctuation behavior of coolant jet mass flow rate (MFR) at the supply cavity inlet and endwall film cooling effectiveness at monitors within the vane passage. At low pulsation amplitude conditions ($K=5\%$), fluctuations in coolant jet MFR and endwall film cooling effectiveness remain at low levels. When high pulsation amplitude ($K=10\%$) conditions are imposed, coolant jet MFR fluctuations are significantly enhanced, particularly at $f=1000$ Hz and $f=5000$ Hz conditions. Nevertheless, markedly enhanced fluctuations in endwall film cooling effectiveness are

noticed only at $f = 1000$ Hz conditions. As discussed above, endwall film cooling behavior is determined by combined impacts of coolant jet flow rate, HV system, SV system, and interactions between coolant jets and mainstream. Fluctuations in coolant jet MFR and endwall film cooling effectiveness closely follow sinusoidal patterns, and their dominant frequency signals perfectly match inflow pulsation frequencies, as confirmed by FFT analysis. This indicates that flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion propagate through turbine vane cascades without frequency attenuation, despite the presence of vortex system dissipation and strong coolant jets disturbance across cascades.

Fig. 19 Pulsatile levels and FFT analysis of monitors within the turbine vane cascades

4. CONCLUSION

To understand the effects of flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion on downstream turbine cascade aerothermal performance, this paper thoroughly investigated endwall film cooling performance of NGV at pulsatile flow conditions. Based on the measured flow pulsation data from realistic hydrogen combustion tests, URANS numerical predictions and FFT spectral analysis were employed to capture near-endwall flow behavior, film cooling effectiveness, and spectral features at three typical pulsation frequencies ($f = 1000$ Hz, 3000 Hz, and 5000 Hz) and two pulsation amplitudes ($K = 5\%$ and 10%). The major findings are summarized as follows:

- 1) Flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion are detrimental to endwall film cooling performance, and the decay presents non-monotonic response with increasing pulsation frequencies. At low pulsation amplitude conditions ($K = 5\%$), minimum reduction (approximately 3.8%) in endwall film cooling effectiveness occurs at $f = 3000$ Hz conditions, with coolant jet coverage comparable to no-pulsation conditions within the vane passage ($0 < x < 0.65 Cx$) of interest in this paper. Higher pulsation

frequencies will significantly reduce endwall film cooling performance, leading to a rapid decrease in magnitudes (up to 10.1% at $f = 5000$ Hz condition).

- 2) Increased pulsation amplitudes ($K = 10\%$) will introduce additional degradation in endwall film cooling performance, with reduction magnitudes exhibiting distinct frequency sensitivity. The reduction magnitudes in film cooling effectiveness decrease rapidly from 14.2% to 0.2% as pulsation frequencies increase from $f = 1000$ Hz to 5000 Hz. At $f = 1000$ Hz conditions, film cooling performance is severely compromised at the vane passage, demonstrating low film cooling effectiveness (0.2-0.3) throughout the entire region.
- 3) Pulsation frequencies have minimal effects on fluctuation amplitudes in endwall film cooling effectiveness, and the fluctuation peaks are limited to below 10% within the vane passage. Nevertheless, fluctuation patterns are closely related to the inflow pulsation frequencies, and several regions with fluctuation peaks are identified, particularly in regions downstream of film holes, near the vane pressure side, and around the vane passage throat. More importantly, dominant frequency signals at multiple monitors within the vane passage perfectly match the inflow pulsation frequencies.
- 4) In general, flow pulsations induced by hydrogen combustion will propagate through turbine cascades without frequency attenuation and considerably diminish film cooling benefits of original film hole layouts. Consequently, to mitigate increased thermal failure risks in turbine components associated with hydrogen addition, the novel and pulsation-resistant film cooling schemes should be redesigned for hydrogen-combustion turbine cascades.

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